

The Impact Of Item-Writing Flaws On Student Test Scores, Pass Rate And Psychometric Properties Of The Test In End Of Clerkship Ophthalmology Assessment

Amena Masrur, Ali Tayyab, Zoeya Ayesha Khan, Sulman Jaffar, Memoona Mansoor, Sumreena Mansoor, Ayesha Rauf, Syed Shoaib Shah

Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>Assessment continues to be a major driver and measure of students' learning & competence. Assessments, therefore, should be designed in a manner as to yield information that accurately and completely describes the degree to which the students have gained requisite knowledge. At the same time, the assessment should be constructed and presented to the students in a manner that is not overly complex. Written assessments, in the context of medical students, are used to test medical knowledge, of all the types of written assessments in current practice, the Multiple-Choice Question (MCQ) is the mainstay written assessment technique. MCQs that are not appropriately constructed or are 'flawed' items, may affect student performance, making the test either relatively difficult or easy.</i></p> <p><i>Method. In this non-experimental observational study, four hundred multiple choice questions from 8 end of clerkship Ophthalmology written assessments were independently scrutinized for item writing flaws by a panel of four expert judges, who noted the flaws on a prescribed form. Based on their findings two optical mark reader keys were generated, one consisting of all questions; the flawed scale, and the other excluding flawed questions; the standard scale. The student optical mark reader sheets were compared against both to generate a standard and flawed scale test data consisting of student pass rate, mean score, mean discrimination & mean difficulty index and test reliability using Laboratory of educational research test analysis package.</i></p> <p><i>Results Sixty item writing flaws were identified. All eight tests showed that item writing flaws affected student performance as well as test psychometrics. Mean scores increased in all standard scales as compared to flawed scales, while pass rate increased in all but four tests; it remained the same in two and was lower in the last two. Mean Discrimination index and reliability also increased in standard scale across all tests. Mean difficulty index increased in all tests but two, it was lower in one, while no change was observed in the other.</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: This study shows that Item writing flaws affect test validity and reliability. Moreover, they also distort the pass rates, penalizing students most of the time.</i></p>
Received: September 01, 2021	
Accepted: April 02, 2022	
Keywords : Assessment, Item Writing Flaws, Student Performance, Reliability	
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6407321	

Introduction

Assessment continues to be a major driver and measure of students' learning & competence. Assessments, therefore, should be designed in a manner as to yield information that accurately and completely reflect the level of competence attained by the students.

Written assessments, in the context of medical students, are used to test medical knowledge which has been defined as the ability to demonstrate knowledge of established and evolving biomedical, clinical, epidemiological and social-behavioral sciences, as well as the application of this knowledge to patient care (Lauer & Lauer, 2017).

Of all the types of written assessments in current practice, the Multiple-Choice Question (MCQ) is the mainstay written assessment technique. However, MCQs that are not appropriately constructed ("flawed items") may affect student performance making the test either relatively difficult or easy (Epstein, 2007; Schuwirth & Vleuten, 2004; Haladyna, Downing & Rodriguez 2001; Downing, 2002). Flawed items also include questions that are contextually poor; those that are designed to test factual knowledge without consideration for applicability to real life clinical presentation or clinical context (McCoubrie, 2004).

Many international governing bodies and regulating authorities in the realm of medical education use the single best type MCQ for undergraduate and postgraduate classroom and high stakes examinations. These include the Australian Medical Council (Blackett, 1990), the General Medical Council of United Kingdom (Oyewole, Animasahun&Chapman, 2020), the Association of American Medical Colleges (Deng, Gluckstein& Larsen, 2015)

Several guidelines are available to ensure that the MCQs constructed are of high quality (Case & Swanson, 2001; Al-Rukban, 2006). Despite availability of guidelines, evidence suggests that most MCQs constructed in-house violate these guidelines, thus reducing the value and the quality of assessments (Downing, 2002; Jozefowicz, Koeppen, Case, Galbraith, Swanson &Glew, 2002)

There are several local and international studies that investigate item writing flaws (Tarrant & Ware, 2008; Downing, 2005; Baig, Ali, Ali & Huda, 2014) however, few measure the impact of writing flaws on student performance; data for clinical written assessments is especially virtually non-existent.

Shifa College of Medicine (SCM) rotates students through clinical clerkships in fourth and final years of their undergraduate training program. The fourth year Ophthalmology clerkship is of 4 weeks duration for each of the 5 rotating clinical groups. Each end of clerkship assessment comprises of 50 MCQs and 10 Short Answer Questions (SAQ). An adhoc score of 50% is taken as pass for all written examinations.

To elucidate whether item writing flaws impact student performance, pass rates & test psychometrics, this study investigated the impact of item-writing flaws, in single best type multiple-choice questions, on student test scores & pass rate in the end of clerkship Ophthalmology written assessments. The impact of item writing flaws on mean item difficulty, mean discrimination index, and reliability of the test were also determined. The former assists in identifying questions that either artificially raise or lower student scores and pass rates while the latter helps determine the effect on reliability and hence the validity of the inference of the assessment results that the MCQs were a part of.

Method

The study was carried out in the department of Ophthalmology SCM, a constituent unit of Shifa Tameer-e-Millat University (STMU). The assessments were designed in the department of Ophthalmology by the clerkship team. The department of Examinations was responsible for test administration, checking & grading of the MCQ test by Optical Mark Reader (OMR), post-hoc analysis, verification & distribution of result to the students. The study was initiated after approval of the proposal from IRB.

Purposive sampling was employed to select a total of 400 MCQs that were included in the end of clerkship Ophthalmology MCQ test. Tests without psychometric analysis and low reliability ($\alpha < 0.50$) were excluded from the study.

A total of 4 judges were selected to review the MCQ test papers for detection of item writing flaws. All judges possessed a major post graduate qualification in Ophthalmology of at-least 4 years duration, had at-least 3 years' experience teaching Ophthalmology to undergraduate students of SCM and had successfully completed in-house workshops on writing MCQs. Written and Informed consent was taken from all the judges. They were not offered any monetary benefit for their participation in the study. They were asked to sign a confidentiality statement preventing them from sharing/ retrieving MCQs in any form for personal gain. All the judges were provided with a copy of and required to go over the National Board of Medical Examiners guidelines for constructing written test questions for the basic and clinical sciences which was provided to them, for reviewing item writing flaws.

All the judges were required to assess each MCQ test for item writing flaws independently of others. One moderator (excluding the judges) was selected to assist with the process of adjudication. The judges were seated in adjoining conference rooms to scrutinize the MCQ test and note item writing flaws on the prescribed form. Each item was judged for all possible writing flaws. An item was considered flawed if it contained ≥ 1 of the listed flaws. In case of discrepancies between judgments, the particular MCQ(s) were discussed by the judges together to reach a consensus. This process was repeated for all MCQ tests.

The frequency of item writing flaws was calculated from the prescribed forms filled in by the judges. Frequency distribution was calculated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 20. Based on the scrutiny of the judges, two test scales were created from each of the MCQ test scrutinized, the flawed and standard scale. The test which included all MCQs was the '*flawed scale*'. Test with omitted flawed items was the '*standard scale*'. Two OMR key sheets were generated; one for flawed scale and one for standard scale (the flawed and the standard key respectively).

The student OMR answer sheets were reanalyzed by the OMR machine against the flawed scale key and the standard scale key. Thus, for every test scrutinized the OMR produced two sets of discrete data; one against the flawed key and one against the standard key. The data generated by reading the OMR sheets was exported to Laboratory of Educational Research Test Analysis Package (LERTAP) Version 5.0 via Microsoft Excel file format. For each scale (flawed and standard) the number of questions, difficulty and discrimination indices, test

scores and reliability (Cronbach's alpha) and pass rate were computed. Pass marks for all assessments were set as 50%. To investigate the impact of item writing flaws the two scales were compared with each other for each test scrutinized.

Results and Discussion

The descriptive statistics of the MCQ tests that were scrutinized for item writing flaws are provided in table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of scrutinized tests

	TESTS							
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
No of items	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
No of Flawed Items	8	7	9	7	6	9	7	7
Items without flaws	42	43	41	43	44	41	43	43
Proportion of flawed items	0.16	0.14	0.18	0.14	0.12	0.18	0.14	0.14

As there are 5 clerkship rounds in one academic year, there are as many (5) MCQ assessments. The tests were scrutinized chronologically, selecting one test from each academic year, until the sampling criteria was met. Thus, two tests from each academic year were analyzed (for a total of 400 MCQs). The tests analyzed were labeled from 'A' to 'H'. The highest number of items without flaws in a test were from test E, (number of items without flaws = 44), while the fewest items without flaws in a test were seen in test C and F, (number of items without flaws = 41). The proportion of flawed items ranged from 0.12 to 0.18 (Table 2).

Table 2: Frequency of item writing flaws in each scrutinized test

Item Writing Flaw	TESTS								Total	%
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H		
Grammatical clues						1	1	1	3	5.00
Logical clues							1	1	3	5.00
Similar words in stem & Key					1	2	1	1	5	8.33
Key is longest option					1	2	1	1	5	8.33
Absolute terms					1	2			3	5.00
Vague terms	1	2	2	2				2	9	15.00
Negative stem	1		1	1					3	5.00
Improbable distractors		1			1		1		3	5.00
Stem fails cover test (unfocused)	3	2	3	2	1	1	2		14	23.33
>1 correct answer	1		1						2	3.33
Redundancy in stem	2	2	2	2	1			1	10	16.67
Total	8	7	9	7	6	9	7	7	60	100

Table 2 lists the frequency of item writing flaws identified by the judges in each test scrutinized. The total number of flaws detected was 60 which is 15% of the total number of questions scrutinized. The most common flaw seen was the failure of the question to pass the cover test implying an unfocused stem. This was detected

14 times which is nearly a third of all flaws at 23.33%. The least common flaw seen was more than one correct answer seen only twice, a percentage share of 3.33% of all item writing flaws detected in this study. The second most common flaw seen was the use redundancy in stem This was seen 10 times (16.67% share of item writing flaws). Grammatical cues, logical cues, absolute terms, negatively phrased stem and implausible distractors were all picked up 3 times. There were several flaw types that were not seen at all in any of the scrutinized assessments in including Options not arranged alphabetically, All and none of the above as options and Fill-in - the -blank type stem.

Table 3 provides a comparative overview of flawed and standard scales (mean score, difficulty and discrimination indices, reliability and pass percentage).

Table 3: Characteristics of Flawed (F) & Standard (S) scale

Test	Mean Score		Mean Difficulty Index		Mean Discrimination Index		Reliability		Pass Percentage	
	F	S	F	S	F	S	F	S	F	S
A	26.00 ±5.83	29.05 ±5.13	0.58 ±0.26	0.60 ±0.26	0.17 ±0.25	0.26 ±0.17	0.68	0.80	81.81	86.36
B	25.30 ±5.10	27.05 ±4.58	0.54 ±0.30	0.59 ±0.29	0.13 ±0.28	0.21 ±0.25	0.63	0.75	70.00	80.00
C	25.00 ±6.37	27.67 ±5.86	0.55 ±0.25	0.60 ±0.29	0.21 ±0.25	0.25 ±0.19	0.74	0.83	72.22	86.39
D	34.42 ±4.74	35.21 ±4.48	0.70 ±0.25	0.74 ±0.24	0.16 ±0.26	0.22 ±0.26	0.64	0.75	94.73	94.73
E	22.20 ±4.49	25.50 ±3.97	0.51 ±0.24	0.52 ±0.24	0.14 ±0.20	0.22 ±0.26	0.60	0.75	60.00	60.00
F	21.62 ±5.11	26.29 ±4.34	0.53 ±0.22	0.51 ±0.23	0.09 ±0.21	0.18 ±0.15	0.50	0.69	61.90	52.38
G	32.60 ±6.21	35.55 ±5.80	0.71 ±0.19	0.72 ±0.18	0.22 ±0.25	0.28 ±0.20	0.76	0.82	85.00	95.00
H	25.26 ±5.29	28.47 ±4.67	0.57 ±0.29	0.57 ±0.29	0.16 ±0.26	0.23 ±0.29	0.64	0.76	84.21	73.68

The analysis of the result shows that flawed items can artificially raise or lower difficulty or have no impact on difficulty at all depending on the type of writing flaw. The analysis further shows that no matter what the type of flaw, removal of flawed items improves discrimination and reliability of test scores. The mean score and pass rate changes reflect underlying changes in the discrimination and difficulty indices as described in the preceding discussion. The standard scale showed higher student scores, than on flawed scales, in all tests assessed. The standard scale also showed that pass rate increased except for test D which showed no change, and tests F and H where the pass rate decreased. Overall, the pass rate improved to 86.36% in standard scale as compared to 72.22 percent in flawed scale; a difference of 14.14 points. The difficulty index increased (tests became easier) in the standard scale, except for test F in which case it decreased and no change was seen in test H. The standard scale discriminated amongst student better in all scrutinized tests as compared to the flawed scale. The Cronbach's alpha was higher for the standard scale as compared to the flawed scale for all tests.

The analysis of the data shows that item writing flaws have an impact on both student performance and psychometric properties of the test. The majority of the tests scrutinized consisted of flawed questions that were

artificially raising the difficulty level of the test. Removing these questions resulted in greater pass rate and improved student scores. A minority (2 of 8 tests scrutinized) of the tests consisted of flawed questions that were making the test easier than intended. Removing these questions resulted in lowering of pass rate. Under all circumstances writing flaws have a negative impact on the test reliability, validity and distort assessment of student performance.

In each of the tests, removing flawed items enhanced validity. Reliability was negatively affected as the discrimination index was negatively affected by flawed items (standard scale in all tests showed an improvement in discrimination index). Discrimination index of the test indirectly influences the test reliability. The Construct validity was affected as writing flaws influenced all sources of validity evidence (Pais, Silva, Guimarães, Povo, Coelho, Silva-Pereira, Lourinho, Ferreira & Severo, 2016). Briefly, Content evidence was affected as the quality of test questions was affected by writing flaws. The response process evidence was affected as writing flaws do not allow accurate interpretation of test scores. Internal structure evidence was affected as its psychometric indices were affected by writing flaws. Similarly, a fair convergent or divergent correlation cannot be made to other tests as long as the test under scrutiny itself is of questionable worth and neither can the interpretation of test scores be generalized. Finally, and perhaps most importantly students are either unfairly declared unsuccessful or successful (which is of greater concern as it distorts what competence has actually been achieved by the student) due to the presence of writing flaws. This affects the consequence evidence of validity which also implies that future revision & use of the item are affected since the items with flaws may continue to be used without review. All of these eventually contribute to construct irrelevance variance, introduced due to writing flaws, which reduce the over-all validity of the test (Downing 2002; Downing 2002).

The majority of the investigations pertaining to this topic are on the detection of item writing flaws rather than their impact. Further, the research on the impact on psychometrics and student performance, is predominantly on data from pre-clinical years whether in medical or para-medical domains. Data from clinical years is virtually non-existent and mixed data (from both pre-clinical and clinical years) is rare (Ware & Vik, 2009). One plausible explanation for this is that in most medical programs the focus in clinical years is on assessment of performance through Workplace Based Assessments (WBAs) and Objectively Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs) or their variants which assess more complex competencies whose basis lie in sound medical knowledge. (Kirton & Kravitz, 2011). Written assessment, which is the focus of this study, only assesses the knowledge domain and usually limited to shelf exams.

The total number of item writing flaws in our study was 60, detected in a scrutiny of 400 MCQs. This translates to a detection rate of 15% which is low compared to the rates of 21% to 70% reported in published literature (Rush, Rankin & White, 2016; Khan, Danish, Awan & Anwar, 2013). The lowest reported rate is by Khan et al, of 21% (2013). However, in the study by Khan et al the item writers had 2 years of experience in writing items. Their initial flaw rate was 67%. When these item writers started to make MCQs, it fell to 36.3% after one year and reached 21% after 2 years of writing questions. The highest reported rate is that of 70% (Rush, Rankin & White, 2016). Experience in item writing has been shown to improve quality of questions generated (Khan, Danish, Awan & Anwar, 2013; Jozefowicz, Koeppen, Case, Galbraith, Swanson & Glew, 2002). This experience can be gained from continual exposure to writing questions or attending workshops pertaining to item writing. The item writers in our study had multiple years of experience and had attended compulsory workshops for development of MCQs. This is the likely explanation for low rates of item writing flaws in our investigations.

The investigation on performance of nursing students shows an interesting comparison (Tarrant & Ware, 2008). The student scores increased in the standard scale as compared to the flawed scale wherever the pass rate increased in the standard scale. In analysis of the tests where pass rate decreased in the standard scale so did the student performance. The explanation provided by the study is that in the case of nursing students, there were more borderline students who gained from flawed items as compared to the high achieving students. As the flawed items were removed the low scoring (borderline) students failed to achieve a pass grade. These students contributed to the higher failure and thus a lower pass rate in their study. Correlating this to their performance it can be concluded that the mean scores decreased as the contribution of these failing students had a greater impact on the score as compared to that of the passing students. This is in contrast to our own findings where the performance (individual student scores) increased irrespective of pass rate in the standard scale. In our study, in the tests where the student test scores increase while pass rate decreases (tests F and H) the borderline students were handicapped by item writing flaws. A few of the borderlines students failed the standard test as they had, in all likelihood, guessed the correct answer to flawed questions, resulting in an artificially higher passing rate in the flawed test. Correlating the student performance data to item writing flaws in the tests, where the relationship between student performance and pass rate is inverse, it can be seen that most item writing flaws in these tests tend to favor guessing and test-wise students.

The comparison of data from preclinical years with clinical year violates validity of inference of performance data as content, consequences and relationship to other variables differ between the clinical and pre-clinical years. Secondly it is not possible to generalize findings of pre-clinical years to clinical years as the domain of

the two, despite the move towards integrated curriculum, is still quite distinct. A study of first- and second-year medical students showed either no change, or an increase in student performance in standard scale as compared to flawed scale (Downing, 2005). The scores increased when the mean difficulty index was higher than intended in the flawed scale. These findings are similar to ours despite the difference between the students' groups tested. A conclusion can be drawn that, across all the tests scrutinized, as many as 7% of the students (n = 11) were unfairly declared fail due to the presence of item writing flaws, while on the other hand 2.5% of the students (n= 5) were declared pass when they had actually not achieved a passing grade. Downing concluded that item writing flaws may be responsible for as many as 15% of the students wrongly declared as failing an assessment when they had performed poorly due to the presence of writing flaws (Downing, 2005). There are psychological, academic and technical implications for both students and teachers. In our specific case, where classroom assessment also contributes to the scores of high-stake year-end University examination as 'internal assessment', a failing grade can mean the student will possibly have to repeat the year. The psychological impact of failing is universal for all students. As for teachers it is one of academic integrity and honesty; the student should not be unfairly judged based on a flaw that is because of the teacher. Technical implications include threats to construct validity of assessment scores as well as flawed compilation of psychometric assessment data for future use of an MCQ.

Seen holistically the mean difficulty index between flawed and standard scales across the 8 tests does not show a great amount of variation which is in agreement with published literature (Tarrant & Ware, 2008; Downing, 2005). The discriminating power of the tests increased in the standard scale as compared to the flawed scale. This means that the flawed items were poor discriminators of student performance and reduced the construct validity of the test results by increasing construct irrelevant variance (Downing, 2002). This fact is also corroborated by Tarrant et al who also observed an improved mean discrimination index as questions with item writing flaws were removed from analysis (Tarrant & Ware, 2008). Downing however reported that discrimination may or may not improve with removal of flawed items (Downing, 2005). This is explained by the hypothesis that if these items were contributing to the score of high achievers, then it is possible that removal of these items would result in lower discrimination.

The reliability of standard scales was higher than that of the flawed scale in all the tests scrutinized in our study. However, this change could not be totally explained on the basis of removal of flawed items, and may have more to do with the increasing discrimination index of the standard scale. Item writing flaws introduce systematic error in the measuring instrument, whereas random errors, caused by unpredictable behaviors, are estimated by Cronbach's alpha (Downing, 2005). It is thus easier to analyze the value of reliability in the context of psychometrics of the test rather than with item writing flaws only. Removing item writing flaws improves student performance, pass rates and mean discrimination index. When comparing item writing flaws to mean difficulty index for these tests, it becomes clear that they contain flaws that are known to inflate difficulty and their removal should make the difficulty index closer to what was intended. The reliability improves as test psychometrics show better properties.

Conclusion

It can be said with confidence that item writing flaws unfairly penalize students, affect test psychometrics which in turn has a negative impact on test reliability. The interplay between writing flaws and test data (test scores & psychometrics) must be done (interpreted) on test-to-test basis to ensure that the principles of validity and reliability are not compromised.

Recommendations

For future research it is recommended that multiple specialties be included, and ideally multiple institutions on a large pool size to ensure collection of data with wider applicability. We also recommend randomization of selection of questions for scrutiny to reduce selection bias.

References

- Al-Rukban M. O. (2006). Guidelines for the construction of multiple choice questions tests. *Journal of family & community medicine*, 13(3), 125–133.
- Baig, M., Ali, S. K., Ali, S., & Huda, N. (2014). Evaluation of Multiple Choice and Short Essay Question items in Basic Medical Sciences. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 30(1), 3–6.
- Blackett R. B. (1990). Foreign medical graduates. The experience of the Australian Medical Examining Council and the Australian Medical Council, 1978-1989: implications for medical immigration and the medical workforce. *The Medical journal of Australia*, 153(3), 125–132.

- Case S. M., & Swanson D. B. (2001). *Constructing Written Test Questions for the Basic and Clinical Sciences*. 3rd ed. Philadelphia: National Board of Medical Examiners.
- Deng, F., Gluckstein, J. A., & Larsen, D. P. (2015). Student-directed retrieval practice is a predictor of medical licensing examination performance. *Perspectives on medical education*, 4(6), 308–313.
- Downing S. M. (2002). Construct-irrelevant variance and flawed test questions: Do multiple-choice item-writing principles make any difference?. *Academic medicine : journal of the Association of American Medical Colleges*, 77(10 Suppl), S103–S104.
- Downing S. M. (2002). Threats to the validity of locally developed multiple-choice tests in medical education: construct-irrelevant variance and construct underrepresentation. *Advances in health sciences education : theory and practice*, 7(3), 235–241.
- Downing, S.M. (2005). The Effects of Violating Standard Item Writing Principles on Tests and Students: The Consequences of Using Flawed Test Items on Achievement Examinations in Medical Education. *Advances in Health Sciences Education*, 10, 133-143.
- Epstein R. M. (2007). Assessment in medical education. *The New England journal of medicine*, 356(4), 387–396.
- Fayyaz Khan, H., Farooq Danish, K., Saeed Awan, A., & Anwar, M. (2013). Identification of technical item flaws leads to improvement of the quality of single best Multiple Choice Questions. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 29(3), 715–718.
- Haladyna, T.M., Downing S.M., & Rodriguez M.C. (2002) A Review of Multiple-Choice Item-Writing Guidelines for Classroom Assessment. *Applied Measurement in Education*, 15:3, 309-333
- Jozefowicz, R. F., Koeppen, B. M., Case, S., Galbraith, R., Swanson, D., & Glew, R. H. (2002). The quality of in-house medical school examinations. *Academic medicine : journal of the Association of American Medical Colleges*, 77(2), 156–161.
- Kirton, S. B., & Kravitz, L. (2011). Objective Structured Clinical Examinations (OSCEs) compared with traditional assessment methods. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 75(6), 111. <https://doi.org/10.5688/ajpe756111>
- Lauer, A. K., & Lauer, D. A. (2017). The good doctor: more than medical knowledge & surgical skill. *Annals of eye science*, 2, 36.
- McCoubrie P. (2004). Improving the fairness of multiple-choice questions: a literature review. *Medical teacher*, 26(8), 709–712.
- Oyewole, B. K., Animasahun, V. J., & Chapman, H. J. (2020). A survey on the effectiveness of WhatsApp for teaching doctors preparing for a licensing exam. *PloS one*, 15(4), e0231148.
- Pais, J., Silva, A., Guimarães, B., Povo, A., Coelho, E., Silva-Pereira, F., Lourinho, I., Ferreira, M. A., & Severo, M. (2016). Do item-writing flaws reduce examinations psychometric quality?. *BMC research notes*, 9(1), 399. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-016-2202-4>
- Rush, B. R., Rankin, D. C., & White, B. J. (2016). The impact of item-writing flaws and item complexity on examination item difficulty and discrimination value. *BMC medical education*, 16(1), 250.
- Schuwirth, L. W., & van der Vleuten, C. P. (2004). Different written assessment methods: what can be said about their strengths and weaknesses?. *Medical education*, 38(9), 974–979.
- Tarrant, M., & Ware, J. (2008). Impact of item-writing flaws in multiple-choice questions on student achievement in high-stakes nursing assessments. *Medical education*, 42(2), 198–206.
- Ware, J., & Vik, T. (2009). Quality assurance of item writing: during the introduction of multiple choice questions in medicine for high stakes examinations. *Medical teacher*, 31(3), 238–243.

Author Information

Dr. Amena Masrur

Associate Professor Department of Ophthalmology
Islamabad Medical and Dental College
Islamabad

Dr. Ali Tayyab

Professor Department of Ophthalmology
Islamabad Medical and Dental College
Islamabad

Zoeya Ayesha Khan

Lausanne Collegiate School
Memphis TN

Dr Sulman Jaffar

Professor Department of Ophthalmology
Shifa College of Medicine Islamabad

Dr. Memoona Mansoor

Assistant Professor, Department of Medical
Education Islamabad Medical and Dental College
Islamabad

Dr Sumreena Mansoor

Professor Department Biochemistry
Shifa College of Medicine Islamabad

Dr Ayesha Rauf

Assistant Dean Curriculum
Department of Health Professionals Education
National University of Medical Sciences
Islamabad

Dr. Syed Shoaib Shah

Dean Health Sciences & Professor
Department of Forensic Medicine
Islamabad Medical and Dental College
Islamabad
